

International Journal of Educational Studies and Policy (IJESP)

Volume: 1, Issue: 1, November 2020

A Phenomenological Study of Graduate Students' Experiences on Flipped Learning in Curriculum Development Course*

İlke Evin Gencil¹

ABSTRACT

Flipped learning is one of the practices brought about by in the field of technology and pedagogy developments. It is referred to by this name since it reverses the conventional understanding of education. Flipped learning offers students a flexible learning environment and access to information on their request. Also, teachers have the opportunity to get to know their students in a better way and to observe their progress rather than focusing on theoretical information during the course. In this study, it was aimed to investigate experiences and views of the graduates on flipped learning in the course of Curriculum Development. For this purpose, the study was designed in accordance with the phenomenological design which is one of the qualitative research methods. The participants of this study were consisted of nine graduate students. The data were collected through a semi-structured interview form and analyzed through content analysis based on coding. Codes were collected under the themes of "contribution to learning", "contribution to the learner", "contribution to the learning environment" and "limitations". Participants generally considered flipped learning positively, however, they stated that it had some limitations such as feeling of being lonely during learning process and technical problems.

Keywords: Flipped learning, instructional design, graduate education, phenomenological design

Article History: Received 14.10.2020

Accepted 03.11.2020

Cite as: Gencil-Evin, İ. (2020). A phenomenological study of graduate students' experiences on flipped learning in curriculum development course, *International Journal of Educational Studies and Policy*, 1(1), 1-14.

¹Corresponding Author: Prof. Dr. İlke Evin Gencil, Izmir Democracy University, ilke.evingencil@idu.edu.tr, ORCID: 0000-0002-2113-701X

* A part of this study was presented at the 27th International Educational Sciences Conference as a summary.

Introduction

Together with the developments in technology and pedagogy, techno-pedagogy have come into prominence and paved the way to the development of strategies to use digital learning elements in instructional designs effectively. Flipped learning is a technology and interaction-based learning model that emerged as a result of these developments (Bishop and Verleger, 2013).

Theoretical Background

Learner-centred education, active learning and transformative learning came into prominence together with the constructivism. Educational practices foregrounding learners' interests and needs, individual differences and learning styles, and giving the responsibility of learning to the students rather than teachers have become widespread (Mezirow, 1997; Prince, 2004); these implementations have taken on a digital dimension with developing technologies, and scientists started to get interested in the blended learning concept intensively. Some researchers consider flipped learning as a form of blended learning. However, while blended learning combines face-to-face and technology-supported interaction factors, flipped learning that is a technology-supported model again carries traditional in-classroom activities to the outside of the classroom and then do the activities in the classroom by using what has been learned before the lesson (Higgitt, 2014). Hwang and Lai (2017) emphasise that recently flipped learning has become the most attractive and innovative learning model.

In the current educational approach, the process of knowledge acquisition generally occurs in the classrooms, while knowledge application occurs through repetitions and assignments out of the classroom after the lessons. On the other hand, in flipped learning, students watch and examine the informative videos/slides out of the classroom and acquire the necessary information. They get involved in the knowledge application and construction process through active learning techniques when they are in classroom settings. Since flipped learning reverses the existing education approach, it is called by this name. In flipped learning, students study the informative videos, short films, presentations or animations prepared by the teacher or the students and available on the Internet as much as needed before the lesson. Bergmann and Sams (2012) indicate that if the lecturers record their own videos in compliance with the objectives of the lesson, it will be more effective on the students.

Flipped learning is based on the four pillars of F-L-I-P identifies the following; F for the flexible environment, L for learning cultures, I for intentional content and P for the professional educator. The flexible environment is important for both students and teachers. Teachers can record the videos or other materials and prepare them in compliance with the objectives of the lesson at any time and place. They can personalise the tools and resources, which they will use, according to the student characteristics. They can create learning spaces by applying effective teaching and learning strategies including face-to-face and distance education strategies. A similar situation applies to the students as well. They also have an opportunity to learn by repetitions and revisions as much as they want and at any suitable time and place for them. Flexible environment plays a role as an important factor to develop both teacher and learner autonomy. Another important component is learning cultures. Contrary to the traditional education, flipped learning assigns the responsibility of learning to the learners with a learner-centred approach and creates a change in the learning culture. Teachers should prepare in-class and out-of-class activities by considering the characteristics of students such as learning styles,

socio-economic status and cognitive abilities. Intentional content is also in close relation to the learning culture. It comprises the planning of all activities such as pre-lesson tasks and in-class and out-of-class applications in line with the objectives of the lesson. The last pillar is defined as a professional educator. The educators should have a role during the process that enables them to think reflectively, stay in touch with students consistently and facilitate the learning process but not control. In this context, the educators should have high-level planning skills; make strategic decisions; be a guide, good evaluator, problem solver and researcher and practitioner at the same time (Flipped Learning Network, 2014; Honeycutt and Garrett, 2014; Ramazani, Graney, Marshall and Sabieh, 2016; Yarbrow, Arfstrom, McKnight and McKnight, 2013).

Implementation of Flipped Learning

It is possible to apply flipped learning in different ways. ‘Flipped 101’ is the basic and common model which is developed by Bergmann and Sams (2014). In this style, learners do the activities such as video-watching and note-taking at home, that is out of the classroom, and in the classroom, they do the activities which require higher-order cognitive skills through active learning. Intensive learner activity in the classroom is an important advantage of this model. Thanks to this model, teachers can allocate some time to apply active learning techniques as well as the arrangements in the activities to meet the individual educational needs of the students. However, the fact that each student needs Internet access is considered as the disadvantage of this model. Students who aren’t able to do the activities assigned as the tasks at home due to financial difficulties will not be able to benefit from in-class activities appropriately when they come to the classroom.

The other flipped learning model ‘In flip’ is developed to solve the Internet access problem mentioned in the flipped learning model 101. In this model, students do all the activities in the classroom. Students watch videos and take notes by benefiting from the Internet access and other technological facilities of the school. Following this process, active learning techniques take place in the classroom again. In this way, each student will have an equal opportunity for the Internet and resource access. Besides, students can ask their questions to their teacher when they study the learning materials since the process continues in control of the teacher (Porter, 2017, Roehl, Reddy and Shannon, 2013).

Another model is called “in flip mastery”. In this model, students learn at their own paces in the classroom as in “in flip” model and do not move on to the next lesson until they reach mastery for the given subject. This situation enables students to feel comfortable. Moving on to the next learning content is possible when all students reach mastery for the given content just as in Bloom’s mastery learning model. An evaluation is made at the end of each section or unit to determine the level of mastery (Porter, 2017).

When the students who take the responsibility of learning come to the classroom, they collaborate actively to do various activities and participate in discussions related to the course subject. By the way, the teacher plays a scaffolding role and provides feedback in this process. Students fulfil their responsibility of learning out of the school with the support of technology and by repeating what they learned as much as they want instead of acquiring theoretical knowledge passively in the classroom. Flipped learning offers a flexible learning environment for students and allows them to reach information when they want. On the other hand, teachers find a chance to get to know their students better and observe their development processes instead of focusing on the delivery of theoretical knowledge during the lesson.

There are research findings related to the fact that flipped learning increases the achievement levels and fosters positive affective attitudes towards learning. Studies also reveal that flipped learning positively affects self-regulation skills and facilitates classroom management. Flipped learning is an educational practice developed by teachers and it doesn't require profound changes in the curriculum. Despite its many positive aspects, research findings are pointing out its limitations as well.

Benefits and Limitations of Flipped Learning

Flipped learning that can be applied in various ways has many advantages. Main advantages are that the students experience active learning process both individually and together with their classmates and find an opportunity to become a self-directed learner (Roehl, Reddy and Shannon, 2013); students have equal opportunities to learn and each student participates in the process actively, the model gives the opportunity to teachers not only to deliver lesson contents but also develop learning and higher-order thinking skills of students (McLaughlin et al, 2014); a continuous feedback exchange is provided between the teacher and the students (Crews and Butterfield, 2014; Hattie, 2009); the model develops positive classroom atmosphere and collaboration (Bergmann and Sams, 2012); the teacher finds an opportunity for self-development and the model can be integrated with problem-based and project-based learning (Estes, Ingram and Liu, 2014); the model also gives the opportunity for individualisation and differentiation in learning (Bergmann and Sams, 2012; Siegle, 2014); and the family members can participate in the learning activities at home (Bergmann and Sams, 2012).

Although flipped learning has many positive features listed above and can also be listed in addition to these, it has some limitations as well. Foremost among these are the problems related to the technical issues and Internet access as mentioned earlier. To eliminate this limitation "in flip" model was developed. In addition, teachers and students should have a high level of self-motivation to fulfil out-of-classroom activities (Siegle, 2014). Teachers need extra time to prepare video records, ppt documents and other preparations especially in the first year of the application (McLaughlin, 2014). Teachers may resist to the implementation of the model let the technology will replace them (Tucker, 2012). The fact that students cannot find an opportunity to ask questions during the learning process is another criticised factor (Milman, 2012). Parents, students and teachers who are used to traditional education systems find flipped learning unhelpful and consider it as an application that downplays teachers (Bergmann and Sams, 2012).

Several studies revealing the positive and limited aspects of flipped learning have been increasingly continuing in various countries and different educational stages. Thaichay ve Sittihitikul (2016) determined that flipped learning made a positive impact on language accuracy and creating an active learning environment at a significant level and that students had positive opinions about the application. Alsawat (2016) determined that the application of the model had a positive impact on the higher-order thinking skills in English and the motivations of the students. In his paper that he analysed 19 studies, Bormann (2014) indicated that there were also studies showing that flipped learning didn't produce positive results on the academic achievement at a significant level, but Bormann added that flipped learning didn't have only one route of application and the results in the analysed studies could have occurred because of the differences in the applications. Francl (2014) stated that the students intensively interacted with each other through flipped learning, and the model improved peer learning and collaboration.

Similarly, See and Conry (2014) indicated that the collaboration among the students and the level of supporting each other increased during the flipped learning practice. McLaughlin and his friends (2013) who work with the students in the health department stated that flipped learning enabled students to control their own learning processes, developed their skills to obtain knowledge from different resources, positively changed their perspectives and reduced their anxiety levels because they came prepared in terms of information and skills. Lou and Li (2018) found out that writing skills in English as a second language developed at a high level through flipped learning and students were satisfied with this application. Millard (2012) emphasised that student participation increased with the application of flipped learning, students improved their teamwork skills, individualised instruction was feasible, and the application allowed the students for creative and authentic thinking. It was stated in many studies carried out with teacher candidates in the literature that flipped learning was an effective model in terms of enabling students to repeat and revise the learning content as much as they want and providing practical and permanent learning (Bishop and Verleger, 2013; Fulton, 2012; Mok, 2014; Pierce and Fox, 2012). Talbert (2012) indicated that the fact that students came to the classroom prepared by watching videos and other materials before the lesson increased the quality of the time spent in the classroom. LaFee (2013) put forward that flipped learning improved students' time management skills, students organised their study hours at home and spent their out-of-classroom times productively. Enfield (2013) stated that technology and the Internet requirements were the limitations of this application and this could cause interruptions in the learning process. Ash (2012) emphasised that the students who were used to traditional education had difficulty to get used to the process, and they still believed that they would learn better if the teacher taught the lesson in the classroom. The researcher emphasised the importance of proper guidance from teachers in this process.

Many studies revealing the positive and negative findings related to flipped learning gives rise to the thought that knowledge accumulation in this domain should increase. In this context, in this study, flipped learning emerging as a learning model in parallel with the developments in technology and pedagogy was applied with the students at the graduate level and the researcher aimed at contributing to the literature by analysing the views of the students on this implementation.

Method

Research Model

This study is designed in accordance with the phenomenological design which is one of the qualitative research methods. Phenomenological design explores how people understand, perceive, and transfer their experiences to their minds (Patton, 2014). Phenomenological design is commonly used in order to get a deeper understanding of a phenomenon (Creswell, 2013; Meriam, 2013). In this study, flipped learning is investigated as a phenomenon. Flipped learning practise lasted 10 weeks in “Curriculum Development” course, including 3 lesson hours in a week. Videos and other materials related to the course contents were shared with students before the lesson and the application studies were conducted with individual and group works during the 3-hours face-to-face education practices.

Participants

Participants of the study were determined through convenience sampling which is one of the purposeful sampling methods. In this way, a case which the researcher can easily access is examined (Zhang and Wildemuth, 2009). The participants of this study were consisted of nine graduate students, including five females and four males, attending master’s classes in the field of Curriculum and Instruction at a state university in the western region of Turkey. Six participants were currently work as teachers and the other three participants were unemployed.

Data Collection Tool

The data was obtained through a semi-structured interview form. The views of two subject-matter experts in the field of curriculum development and measurement and evaluation were received for the preparation of the interview form after the literature reviews. The interview form included four questions to determine the views of the participants regarding flipped learning. Interviews were lasted for 30-35 minutes and recorded. After the transcription, voice recordings were written, submitted to the participants for checking and participants’ approvals were received.

Data Analyses

Data was analysed through content analysis based on coding. Participants’ statements received during the interviews were quoted directly and the quotations were interpreted holistically. Two different experts in educational sciences were conducted the coding process and monitor compliance between the views were provided.

Validity and Reliability

The dimensions of internal reliability (consistency), external reliability (verifiability), internal validity (credibility) and external validity (transferability) were paid attention to in the qualitative research activities. In this study, two different researchers carried out coding for the content analysis and the determined that the match percentage of the themes created at the end of coding was 87%. This result was the indication the high internal consistency. Coding notes on the interview form contents kept as transcript records were preserved to provide the verifiability of the study. The trustworthiness of the study was provided by enabling participants to control the interview transcripts and quoting the examples to the participants’ statements directly and without making any changes in the stage of the data interpretation. Explanation of the research design, participants, data collection and data analysis processes were considered as the

transferability indicator. To eliminate the researcher bias collected data was reported in detail and another researcher participated in the coding process as well (Roberts and Priest, 20016).

Findings

Codes reached as a result of the inductive content analysis were collected under the themes of “contribution to learning”, “contribution to the learner”, “contribution to the learning environment” and “limitations”. Codes and themes are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Codes and Themes Reached Through Content Analysis

Codes	Themes
Active learning Permanence Repetition In-depth learning	Contribution to Learning
Autonomy Responsibility Motivation Self-confidence Progressing at one’s own pace	Contribution to Learner
Fun Communication Flexibility Application	Contribution to Learning Environment
Having difficulty Loneliness Technical problems	Limitations

Findings related to the Theme “Contribution to Learning”

Codes under this theme were listed as active learning, preparation to the lesson, permanence, repetition and in-depth learning. P1: “... we were applying active learning in some lessons but none of them was like flipped learning. Active learning occurred both out of the classroom when we study the learning materials, watch the videos and in the classroom.” P5: “... I think the most important aim of us as teachers is to enable the actualisation of active learning. I saw that the actualisation of this aim was so easy with flipped learning that I hadn’t ever encountered. When the professor sends the videos to us, we don’t only watch them, we are active at that moment, too. We take notes, draw questions in our own ways and when we went to the class, for example, we were active again by applying the needs analysis techniques in the curriculum development that we had already learnt out of the classroom.

P8 “watching videos, pausing where I want and watching again is like having the professor as a guest at my home so to speak, it increased the learning permanence extremely. If you happen to ask me about the curriculum development models now, firstly the videos and the presentation files that I watched and then our in-class activities regarding these models swim before my eyes. I guess the keyword for me is per-ma-nence (laughing)” P5: “If someone happens to ask me questions about the lessons that I received during my graduate education, I am sure I will unhesitatingly remember what I learned in the curriculum development courses. Very suitable for learning by doing and living that is always said...”

P4: “we have very important freedom in flipped learning: repetition. They say that repetition is the mother and father of learning (laughing). Does our lecturer try to teach me the same subject over and over again? No, I can give you many reasons such as time isn’t enough, it won’t be appropriate for others. However, flipped learning enabled me to learn through the repetitions as much as I want.” P9 “It seemed to me as if I would memorise and then forget since the curriculum development is actually a theoretical lesson but I revised the subjects as much as I wanted out of the classroom, when we did the activities in the classroom, actually the learning occurred spontaneously.

P7 “If this course was taught with traditional education, I wouldn’t be able to learn like this. Because curriculum development course includes too many abstract and theoretical subjects and we are supposed to learn their practical parts. If it were limited to face-to-face education for three lessons in a week, we would merely learn that theoretical part. But, since we learnt the theory through flipped learning and then came to the classroom, we did activities, for example, we created an example to the layered curriculum or created tables related to the topics, summaries, discussions... All of these prompted us to learn in-depth just as it should be in a graduate programme. Otherwise, it would be superficial, for sure...” and P3: “we had the opportunity to make the most of our lecturer’s experience and practices since we came here after we studied and learnt out of the classroom. Time wasn’t wasted with lecturing. To me, permanent and in-depth learning occurred since learning tasks and reflection questions came with the videos...”

As it is seen, the participants specified with examples that flipped learning has positive contributions to learning.

Findings related to the Theme “Contribution to the Learner”

Codes under this theme were determined as autonomy, responsibility, motivation, self-confidence and progressing at one’s own pace. P1 “our lecturer is here, but as if she isn’t, I mean she isn’t here as a traditional educator. While learning, I learnt with her directions without controlling. While applying, I learnt with her directions again. That is as if I was doing everything by myself to learn” P4: “I was planning in my mind at first when the learning materials reached me. I was thinking how much time I should have allocated to what, then again, how I should have taken notes. Directing the process, the way I want and making decisions were among the most important points that I can say positive.

Examples of statements received under the code responsibility are as follows. P1: “I tried to see it from different perspectives as I am a teacher, too, I thought how I would apply this... Our general mistake as teachers is that we mostly feel and act as if we are responsible for the learning of the students, I think. That is, of course, we are but what I mean is the student is the only one who will actually do this task and flipped learning, I think, reminds the students of this task”, P2: “we benefit from both digital resources and the knowledge of our lecturer but we also feel that the actual work in on us...” P8: “ Definitely, my desire to learn and motivation increased. We are doing activities with our friends in our face-to-face lessons. Distraction or boredom wasn’t in question in any way. I can’t even say I sometimes didn’t imagine myself like I was in the Bond movies (laughing) because a video is coming, you are studying it, learning, doing other tasks... A practice keeping students’ attention alive” and P6: “Maybe it isn’t so relevant but I remember, I learnt that each student experienced the feeling of success in the

mastery learning model. The mastery learning model isn't in compliance with flipped learning in terms of their philosophies but the success is experienced in flipped learning as well, you feel you learn, this motivates you, you become inclined to learn more..."

P5 *"you are ready for the lesson, you studied before, you don't have a thought like I wish nobody would ask me any questions, because you are confident. And again P9: "the classroom environment is a sharing environment rather than learning. Everyone worked out the most boring part of the job out of the classroom and came, we share by doing activities in the group works together. We have self-confidence in the classroom since we get prepared before the lesson" P3: "much as we are graduate students now, we may avoid asking questions or saying that we don't understand. Maybe we avoid more because we are graduate students. Or we don't have the opportunity to revise the content over and over again when the lecturer teaches. Sometimes we fall behind, sometimes we grasp before anyone else but finally, time is always a challenge. At least this is the situation for me. However, I didn't have such a problem with flipped learning. I had the opportunity to revise and allocate time as much as I want." and P8 "with this practice, I think each student can make progress in line with his/her own preferences. One can make progress by using visuals while the other one by summarising by allocating time as much as they want".*

Based on participants' statements, it can be said that flipped classroom enabled graduates' to be autonomous learner, reinforced their motivation and self-confidence

Findings related to the Theme "Contribution to the Learning Environment"

Codes under this theme were determined as entertainment, communication-collaboration, flexibility, and application. Examples to the participants' statements are as follows. P6: *"especially the active learning techniques that we applied created a fun atmosphere in the classroom. We couldn't find the chance of applying by having fun at the graduate classes. It was good in this respect."* P4: *"it was both online and face-to-face and this made things enjoyable."* P9: *"our communication with both our lecturer and friends gained strength together with this application, we learned together with our friends, we supported each other. And what is more, the experience is going on, that is in the traditional education, you go to the class, the lesson is taught, then you go out and the next week you go to the class again, In this application, however, it doesn't end, that is, when the lesson is over, the video materials of the next week come, in that period, you look at them continuously, learn, and in the classroom, we can ask our lecturer or friends, I can say that there is a perpetual interaction. And P1: "it provides with a flexible environment for the learning period and time, learning environment, and activities. I think it is very suitable for the ones who work and study like us". Another statement received under the code of flexibility belongs to P7: "I benefited from different resources, too. I didn't keep myself limited only with the videos that the lecturer sent. Moreover, I sometimes found an opportunity at late hours and I sometimes listened with earphones on the public bus. I went through different learning processes. Doing activities with different techniques was favourable during face-to-face education. It was a multi-choice application."*

P5 *"We tested the curriculum development implementations face-to-face in the classroom. Because we were prepared to do these out of the classroom. It was good to find a chance to apply in such a verbal lesson."* And P2: *"our lessons are generally theoretical, and I always have a question in my mind like I will be a scientist and will I be efficient enough when I*

have to develop a curriculum. Flipped learning contributed to both inking theoretical knowledge in and transferring this knowledge into practice”.

According to participants views, it can be said that they were positive about the learning environment through flipped learning practise.

Findings related to the Theme “Limitations”

Negative views of the participants regarding flipped learning application were collected under the theme of “limitations” with the codes of having difficulty, loneliness and technical problems. Participants’ views regarding the flipped learning practise were generally positive as they are seen in the titles above. Nevertheless, three participants mentioned the limitations of the application. For example, while P2 explains *“it has many positive aspects but there were the occasions that I had difficulty. Maybe this was because of the content of the lesson. There are some abstract topics in the curriculum development course and from time to time, I thought if the teacher had explained these directly in the classroom.”* P9 told *“both the moderate environment in the classroom and the provision of active learning were in question and I was very pleased but, in this process, I moved my house. It took time to get an Internet connection. Considering this, I think flipped learning is an application through which technical problems can be experienced.”* P4 reflected his/her opinions with the expressions *“I myself decided what I will study, how much and how and this was good but I also happened to feel alone as a student in this process”.*

Based on participants’ statements, it can be said that graduates had some difficulties during the flipped learning practise as explained above. These opinions should take consideration for future flipped learning implementation.

Discussion, Conclusion and Suggestions

In this study, views of a group of graduate students were examined related to flipped learning developed as a consequence of a paradigm shift which technology created in the field of education. Participants generally considered flipped learning positively, however, they stated that it had some limitations as well. This finding complies with many studies in the literature (Bergmann and Sams, 2012; Bishop and Verleger, 2013; Foster and Stagl, 2018; O’Flaherty and Phillips, 2015; Thaichay and Sittihitikul, 2016). Considering the Wannar and Palmer’s (2015) indication that flipped learning application is effective on the development of flexible and transformative universities, we can interpret that flipped learning can be used effectively not only at the undergraduate level but also at the graduate level.

The participants stated that active, effective and permanent learning occurred, in-depth learning was provided even in a course like the curriculum development which includes abstract content. Similarly, Bergmann and Sams (2012), Ramazani et al. (2016), Kim, Park and Joo (2014) also emphasise the influence of flipped learning on effective and permanent learning. The participants indicated that the availability to revise the video contents and learning materials as much as they wanted, created a positive effect on their learning. Bishop and Verleger (2013), Fulton (2012), Mok (2014) and Pierce and Fox (2012) also remarked that the opportunity of an unlimited number of repetitions is one of the important advantages in flipped learning. Participants emphasised other particulars that their autonomy, responsibility, self-confidence and motivations increased, and they found an opportunity to learn at their own pace. These statements support the other findings in the literature (Alsowat, 2016; Lafee, 2013; Porter, 2017).

Another finding is the views of the participants that flipped learning created a funny and flexible environment with a communication-based collaboration, Strayer (2012), Estes, Ingram and Liu (2014), Honeycutt and Garrett (2014) and Ramazani et al. (2016) also specified that the flexible and enjoyable environment created with flipped learning had a positive effect on learning. Bergmann and Sams (2012) and See and Conry (2014) indicated that flipped learning applications supported peer learning and collaboration.

Three participants mentioned the limitations of the application, and these were grouped as technical challenges, having difficulty because of old learning habits, the feeling of loneliness in the learning process. Siegle (2014) and Bergmann and Sams (2012) also considered the technical possibilities and the Internet access requirement as the limitation of the application. This limitation can be eliminated with the practices such as “in flip” model as it was mentioned in the previous sections. The views regarding the lack of the opportunity to ask questions to the teacher in the process that out-of-classroom learning occurs (Milman (2012) and the fact that students who are used to traditional education can have a difficulty (Bergmann and Sams, 2012) were encountered in the literature. This limitation can be eliminated by creating an information exchange platform or forum pages where students can ask questions to their teachers or each other during the learning process at home. In addition, it was stated that the students who resisted to the application took pleasure in flipped learning in time (Bergmann and Sams, 2012).

Considering that the students and especially the digital natives among them have limited attention spans flipped learning is a practice which makes an important contribution to the occurrence of effective learning with the choices that it offers. The model can be regarded as an alternative way not only for academic learning but also for enabling students to be self-learners, and it motivates individuals to be lifelong learners and to grow as individuals having 21st-century basic skills. Flipped learning was applied in this study in the curriculum development course, one of the basic courses for the graduate students attending curriculum and instruction programme and can be applied in the other courses as well. In this study, students were interviewed, and the results were interpreted. Collecting data through quantitative and qualitative data analysis with studies designed in accordance with research methods such as quasi-experimental, experimental or action research will contribute to the literature. The COVID-19 pandemic hadn't started in the world yet when this research was carried out. However, in spite of the interruptions in the educational processes with this outbreak, problems lived to organise face-to-face training, the opportunity to meet the students only on certain days and hours of the week have shown that flipped learning is a learning model that can be applied in extraordinary global conditions.

References

- Alsowat, H. (2016). An EFL flipped classroom teaching model: Effects on English language higher-order thinking skills, student engagement and satisfaction. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7 (9), 108-121.
- Ash, K. (2012). Educators view 'flipped' model with a more critical eye. *Education Week*, 32 (2), 56-57.
- Bergmann, J. & Sams, A. (2012). *Flip your classroom: Reach every student in every class every day*. Washington, DC: International Society for Technology in Education.
- Bergmann, J., & Sams, A. (2014). Flipping for mastery. *Educational Leadership*, 71(4), 24-29.
- Bishop, J. L., & Verleger, M. A. (2013). *The flipped classroom: A survey of the research*. ASEE National Conference, Atlanta, GA.
- Bormann, J. (2014). *Affordances of flipped learning and its effects on student engagement and achievement* (Unpublished master's dissertation). University of Northern, Iowa.
- Creswell, J. W. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Crews, T., & Butterfield, J. (2014). Data for flipped classroom design: Using student feedback to identify the best components from online and face-to-face classes. *Higher Education Studies*, 4 (3), 38-47.
- Enfield, J. (2013). Looking at the Impact of the Flipped Classroom Model of Instruction on Undergraduate Multimedia Students at CSUN. *TechTrends: Linking Research and Practice to Improve Learning*, 57(6), 14-27.
- Estes, M. D., Ingram, R., & Liu, J. C. (2014). A review of flipped classroom research, practice, and technologies. *International HETL Review*, 4 (7), URL: <https://www.hetl.org/feature-articles/a-review-of-flipped-classroom-research-practice-and-technologies>.
- Flipped Learning Network (FLN). (2014). *What is flipped learning?* Retrieved from [http://fln.schoolwires.net/cms/lib07/VA01923112/Centricity/Domain/46/FLIP handoutFLN_Web.pdf](http://fln.schoolwires.net/cms/lib07/VA01923112/Centricity/Domain/46/FLIP%20handout%20LN_Web.pdf).
- Foster, G., & Stagl, S. (2018). Design, implementation, and evaluation of an inverted (flipped) classroom model economics for sustainable education course. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 183, 1323-1336.
- Francl, T. J. (2014). Is flipped learning appropriate?. *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching*, 7(1), 119-128.
- Fulton, K. (2012). Upside down and inside out: Flip your classroom to improve student learning. *Learning & Leading with Technology*, 12-17.
- Hattie, J. (2009). *Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Higgitt, D. (2014). Disruptive moments. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 38(1), 1-6.

- Honeycutt, B., & Garrett, J. (2014). Expanding the definition of a flipped learning environment. In *Blended and flipped: Exploring new models for effective teaching and learning*, Magna Publications.
- Hwang, G. J., & Lai, C. L. (2017). Facilitating and bridging out-of-class learning: An interactive e-book based flipped learning approach for math course. *Educational Technology & Society*, 20 (1), 184-197.
- Kim, S., Park, N., & Joo, K., (2014). Effects of flipped classroom based on smart learning on self-directed and collaborative learning. *International Journal of Control and Automation*, 7(12), 69-80.
- LaFee, S. (2013). Flipped learning. *The Education Digest*, 79 (3) 13-18.
- Lou, Y., & Li, Z. (2018). Effects of form-focused instruction in the flipped classroom model on non-English-majored graduates' English writing. *Asian Education Studies*, 3(2), 61-68.
- McLaughlin, J. E., Roth, M. T., Glatt, D. M., Gharkholonarehe, N., Davidson, C. A., Griffin, L. M. & Mumper, R. J. (2014). The flipped classroom: a course redesign to foster learning and engagement in a health professions school. *Academic Medicine*, 89(2), 236-243.
- Merriam, S. B. (2009). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Mezirow, J. (1997) Transformative learning theory to practice. *New Directions for Adult and Continuing Education*, 74, 5-12.
- Milman, N. B. (2012). The flipped classroom strategy: What is it and how can it best be used? *Distance Learning*, 9 (3), 85.
- Millard, E. (2012). 5 reasons flipped classrooms work. *University Business*, 26-29.
- Mok, H. N. (2014). Teaching tip: The flipped classroom. *Journal of Information Systems Education*, 25(1), 7-11.
- O'Fkaherty, J., & Phillips, C. (2015). The use of flipped classrooms in higher education: A scoping review. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 25, 85-95.
- Patton, M. Q., (2014), *Qualitative research & evaluation methods integrating theory and practice* (Fourth Edition), Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Pierce, R., & Fox, J. (2012). Vodcasts and active-learning exercises in a flipped classroom model of a renal pharmacotherapy module. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 76 (10), 1-5.
- Porter, D. R. (2017). *A transition to flipped learning: The Oakfield experience*. Education and Human Development Master's Theses. 739.
https://digitalcommons.brockport.edu/ehd_theses/739.
- Prince, M. J. (2004). Does active learning work? A review of the research. *Journal of Engineering Education* 93:223-231.

- Ramazani, C. B., Graney, J. M., Marshall, H. W., & Sabieh, C. (2016). Flipped learning in TESOL: Definitions, approaches, and implementation. *TESOL Journal*, 7 (2), 429-437
- Roberts, P., & Priest, H. (2006). Reliability and validity in research. *Nursing Standard*, 20, 41-45.
- Roehl, A., Reddy, S., & Shannon, G. (2013). The flipped classroom: An opportunity to engage millennial students through active learning strategies. *Journal of Family & Consumer Sciences*, 105(2), 44-49.
- See, S., & Conry, J. M. (2014). Flip my class! A faculty development demonstration of a flipped classroom. *Currents in Pharmacy Teaching and Learning*, 6 (4), 585-588.
- Siegle, D. (2014). Differentiating instruction by flipping the classroom. *Gifted Child Today*, 37(1), 51-55.
- Strayer, J. F. (2012). How learning in an inverted classroom influences cooperation, innovation and task orientation. *Learning Environments Research*, 15, 171-193.
- Talbert, R. (2012). Inverted classroom. *Colleagues*, 9 (1), 1-3.
- Thaichay, T., & Sitthitikul, P. (2016). Effects of the flipped classroom instruction on Language accuracy and learning environment: A case study of Thai EFL upper-secondary school students. *Rangsit Journal of Educational Studies*, 3 (2), 35-64.
- Tucker, B. (2012). The Flipped classroom. *Education Next*, 12 (1), 82-83.
- Wanner, T., & Palmer, E. (2015). Personalizing learning: Exploring student and teacher perceptions about flexible learning and assessment in a flipped university course. *Computers and Education*, 88, 354-369.
- Yarbro, J., Arfstrom, K. M., McKnight, K., & McKnight, P. (2014). *Extension of a review of flipped learning*. Pearson, George Mason University.
- Zhang, Y., & Wildemuth, B. M. (2009). Qualitative analysis of content. In B. Wildemuth (Ed.), *Applications of Social Research Methods to Questions in Information and Library Science* (pp.308-319). Westport, CT: Libraries Unlimited.